

ROLE LOADING CONDITIONS ON THE MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF PMMA FROM MOLECULAR DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

We use molecular dynamics (MD) with the DREIDING force field to characterize the mechanical response of amorphous PMMA including yield and post yield phenomena for various loading conditions. We studied periodic systems with linear dimensions 24 nm and five loading conditions: including volume-conserving shear and uniaxial strain, several non-volume conserving uniaxial tension and isotropic expansion. We find that the pressure-modified von Mises criteria (with critical effective yield stress proportional to hydrostatic pressure) can describe our MD results accurately and with pressure sensitivity in excellent agreement with experiments. The yield stress for zero pressure obtained from MD is about 20% larger than the experimental value due to the large strain rates in the MD simulations.

Keywords: molecular dynamics, PMMA, thermoplastic, mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the molecular origins of the mechanical response of amorphous polymers remains one of the main challenges in materials science. Such an understanding and the resulting computational models have the potential to help design new materials with improved properties and affect a wide variety of established industries like aerospace and electronics and emerging technologies like micro-electromechanical systems [1]. The mechanical response of crystalline materials is understood in terms of processes involving the motion of defects including dislocations, grain boundaries and vacancies and such understanding enables and informs physics-based models capable of predicting the mechanical response of these materials. Even though defects like shear bands are known to play a key role in the deformation of amorphous materials [2] and the development of thermodynamically consistent viscoelastic models [3] and fracture models our understanding of this class of materials remains significantly more empirical than for crystalline materials due, in part, to the lack of periodicity in the underlying atomic structures. Atomistic simulations have the potential to contribute significantly to fill this gap in understanding as increase in computing power enables larger-scale simulations and advances in simulation techniques improve the accuracy of the predictions. In this paper we use large-scale molecular dynamics (MD) simulations to characterize the

mechanical response of amorphous PMMA samples under various loading conditions focusing on yielding. We find that a pressure modified von Mises yield criteria can describe the response observed in MD with a pressure sensitivity factor in excellent agreement with experiments.

2. SIMULATION DETAILS

We use the DREIDING force field [5] to describe interactions between atoms; DREIDING describes the total energy as a sum of covalent (bond stretch, angle bending, torsions and improper torsions), van der Waals, and electrostatic interactions. Partial atomic charges for electrostatic interactions are obtained with the Gasteiger method [6] and a cutoff of 12 Å is used for all non-bond interactions. All MD simulations are performed using the LAMMPS code from Sandia National Laboratories [7].

To build the atomic models of the amorphous polymer we use a three step approach: i) we use the rotational isomeric state (RIS) method to build a molecular system at low density consisting of 1080 PMMA chains each with 96 monomers. 80% of the chains are syndiotactic and 20% atactic. ii) The low-density sample is compressed using molecular dynamics at T=600 K using NVT molecular dynamics. iii) The sample corresponding to zero pressure is then cooled down using constant pressure and temperature MD (NPT ensemble) in steps of 25 K every 20 ps. The resulting density of our amorphous samples at T=300 K is 1.24 g/cm³, only 5% larger than the experimental value of 1.18 g/cm³ [8].

Once well a well-equilibrated sample is obtained we use non-equilibrium MD to characterize the mechanical response of the material to a variety of loading conditions. The simulation cell is deformed in small increments at each MD step using the following strain tensor:

$$\Delta\epsilon = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\epsilon_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\nu_y\Delta\epsilon_0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\nu_z\Delta\epsilon_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

We report on 5 deformation pathways: i) pure-shear with $\nu_y=1$ and $\nu_z=0$; ii) volume conserving uniaxial with $\nu_y=\nu_z=0.5$, iii) Uniaxial with Poisson ratio $\nu_y=\nu_z=0.33$; iv) Pure uniaxial strain: $\nu_y=\nu_z=0$; v) isotropic expansion: $\nu_y=\nu_z=-1$. Temperature during the simulations is controlled via a Nose-Hoover thermostat with coupling constant of 0.1 ps and the strain rate $\Delta\epsilon_0/\Delta t$, where Δt is the MD time step, is $3.75 \cdot 10^8$ 1/s.

3. RESULTS

To compare the results of the different loading conditions we divide both stress and strain into their deviatoric and volumetric (or hydrostatic) components. The effective (deviatoric) stress is defined as:

$$\sigma_{eff} = 1/2 \left[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

where σ_i denote stress components along principal axes; we define effective strain in a similar fashion:

$$\varepsilon_{eff} = 1/2 \left[(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2)^2 + (\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_3)^2 + (\varepsilon_3 - \varepsilon_1)^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

where strain components are also given in principal axes. The pressure provides information regarding the volume-changing component of the stress tensor:

$$P = -1/3(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3) \quad (4)$$

and volumetric strain is the corresponding property:

$$\varepsilon_v = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3 \quad (5)$$

In Figure 1 we show the effective stress vs. effective strain for the various loading conditions. We can see that both volume conserving deformations (pure shear and uniaxial with Poisson ratio 0.5) lead to essentially identical effective stress-strain behaviour. The remaining uniaxial tension deformation simulations involve volume expansion and our results show a decrease in effective stress with decreasing density.

Figure 1. Effective stress vs. effective strain for various loading conditions from our MD simulations.

These results indicate the possibility of using a pressure-modified von Mises yield criteria to describe our simulations. In Figure 2 we show the effective yield stress as a function of the corresponding pressure at the yield; we define the yield point of each simulation from the data shown in Figure 1 using an offset of 1% effective strain. Figure 2 shows how decreasing pressure (and consequently density) leads to a decrease in yield stress. To describe our simulation results we use the pressure modified von Mises criteria where at the yield surface the effective stress is linearly related to pressure:

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_{yield} - \mu P \quad (6)$$

where σ_{yield} and μ are the zero pressure yield stress and pressure sensitivity parameter, respectively. Fitting our MD data using Eq. (6) we obtain $\mu=0.36$ and $\sigma_{yield} = 75.9$ MPa.

The MD pressure sensitivity parameter is in excellent agreement with the experimental data in Ref [9] 0.345. The zero pressure yield stress obtained from MD is higher than the experimental value of 59 MPa [9]; this overestimation is likely due to the extremely large strain rates in the MD simulations.

Figure 2. Yield criteria obtained from MD simulations. Effective yield stress as a function of pressure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We used large-scale MD simulations to characterize the mechanical response of PMMA under a variety of loading conditions. The key findings of this work are: i) volume conserving deformations lead to a universal effective stress-effective strain relationship. ii) the effective yield stress decreases linearly with pressure and a pressure-modified von Mises yield criteria can describe the MD data. In general we find good agreement between our MD results and experiments. The predicted density of amorphous PMMA is within 5% of the experimental value. The effective yield stress vs. pressure curve is also in good agreement with experiments; the slope of the curve is predicted within 2% of experiments and the theoretical zero pressure yield stress about 20% larger than experiments due likely to the fast deformation rates in the simulations.

Our results show that MD simulations can provide valuable information regarding the mechanical response of amorphous polymers including quantitative predictions. Such simulations have the potential to help uncover the molecular mechanisms responsible for inelastic deformation in this class of materials.

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